

ISic1285

I.Sicily inscription 1285

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 275 + 302

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κεῖ

2. τε Ἄστé

3. ρις νήπιος

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Here lies Asteris, an infant

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492890

EDCS 39101654

PHI 140775

PHI 316311

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1285. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4352295>